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AAL and the main approaches to balancing interests in European law

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Abstract

AAL systems offer valuable features like fall detection and medication reminders, yet they also raise privacy concerns, especially when utilizing visual data. Balancing competing interests emerges as a potential solution. However, the concept lacks precise definitions, leaving ambiguity about the balancing process. This contribution delves into the methodology of balancing in European law, starting with elucidating the principal dimensions of the balancing metaphor: proportionality and compromising.

Introduction

As the European population ages, the demand for supporting older adults in maintaining independence and quality of life grows exponentially. In his context, video-based Active and Assisted Living (AAL) technologies emerge as a beacon of hope. Numerous studies assert that AAL technologies will continue to improve their ability to assist individuals in need (Aleksic et al., 2022).

Such an optimistic prospect must be juxtaposed to a number of concerns (Ake-Kob et al., 2022). For example, the very sensors that provide critical assistance also

pose a threat to the sanctity of personal space (Arning & Ziefle, 2015). That raises a question: what shall we sacrifice to receive the care we need? There are also other conflicts of interests, going beyond personal dilemmas. Can family or public authorities require older adults to use the most efficient ways of care despite personal objections? Furthermore, as AAL is subject to legal frameworks, to what extent do conflicts between norms and rights pose a problem?

Balancing is one of the plausible approaches to the conflicts of interests. That presents an issue of balancing as a conflict resolution tool, its forms, and effectiveness. In the legal context, the problem is more specific: what is balancing, and how could it be used to prevent or solve conflict? While the concept of balancing has been explored in legal scholarship (Cali, 2007; Van Der Sloot, 2016), it lacks a universally recognised procedure or a comprehensive inventory of legal instruments of balancing. Furthermore, previous discussions on balancing have predominantly occurred within the context of constitutional law and fundamental rights. Hence, the emergence of innovative technologies, typified by AAL, introduces a novel context to the already examined legal matter.

Balancing within European law

In European law, the concept of balancing has been used predominantly in the area of fundamental rights law. Invoking the concept of balancing does not entail the use of a uniform method of action. In most instances, the ECtHR conducts a seemingly quantitative balancing exercise that is both open-ended and ad hoc (Besson, 2017), entailing a concrete assessment of interests within the particular case (Gerards, 2009).

The conducted research identifies two primary approaches or dimensions of balancing in European law. The first, often referred to as proportionality, involves assigning comparative weights to the interests at stake to ascertain which should prevail (Greer, 2004; Van Der Sloot, 2016). The second approach aims to resolve conflicts of rights or interests by accommodating each involved interest partially. I propose labelling this method as compromising due to its resemblance to compromise.

Balancing as proportionality

Proportionality involves weighing competing interests to determine which should take precedence. This form of balancing primarily concerns the restriction of individual rights and their justification. It may also apply to clashes between stakeholders' interests (Leigh, 2012).

Proportionality involves evaluating a restriction of interest and the justification of the limitation. This method commences with the limitation under consideration

and assesses its legality, necessity, suitability, and proportionality *sensu stricto* (PSS). The PSS is a core concept of balancing as proportionality. PSS entails ensuring that the least restrictive measure is applied and weighing the limitation of an interest caused by the least restrictive measure against the satisfaction of the other interest (Alexy, 2003; Greer, 2004).

Balancing as compromising

The alternative approach to balancing is compromising. Compromising seeks a potential solution for the problem at hand that would satisfy, at least partially, all the interests in question (Van Der Sloot, 2016). This approach commences with a particular problem at hand, for example, a conflict of interests or a technological phenomenon.

The process of compromising is governed by principles of 1) hierarchy of rights/interests, 2) consideration of all interests at stake, 3) equality of rights/interests, 4) avoidance of domination, and 5) specificity of balancing.

Conclusions

Proportionality and compromising represent two distinct dimensions of balancing, embodying disparate approaches, and functioning as disparate metaphors. However, they do not appear to be mutually exclusive. Rather, they may complement each other.

Proposing a method of balancing that reconciles proportionality and compromising would be a significant theoretical contribution with practical implications. Hence, it should be a subject of further research.

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